

**ELECTION BEHAVIOR IN COMMUNITIES OF MENTAYA
RIVER FLOWS IN LEGISLATIVE GENERAL ELECTION IN 2014
BAAMANG SUBDISTRICT, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

Baamang sub-district community is very diverse with a very multiethnic professional background, education, religion, culture and ethnicity. The dynamics of the community need to be reviewed further in relation to the implementation of elections, especially regarding political participation and voter behavior. There are at least seven domains of voters in determining the basis of their political choices, namely, political issues and policies, social image, emotional feelings, candidate image, current events, personal events and epistemic factors. This study aims to determine voter behavior and what factors influence voter behavior in public elections in the Mentaya river basin in the 2014 legislative elections in Baamang sub-district, Kotawaringin Timur, Kalimantan Tengah. The research approach uses qualitative research because the research problems studied are holistic, complex, dynamic and full of meaning. The research method is field research which is a type of research oriented to empirical data collection in the field. The data collection technique in this study was carried out by interview, some notes that became field findings and available documentation related to this study. Data analysis is done by using several main steps, namely reducing data and presenting process data processing data that has been reduced in the form of a brief description describing the findings of the study. The results of the research on voter behavior in the watershed indicate that there are several factors that influence voter behavior namely similarity in identity background, education of candidates, experience of legislative candidates, economy, candidates vision and mission programs, disappointment with the performance of previous legislators and the popularity and appearance of candidates. Whereas voter behavior can be categorized into three namely rational-critical, traditional-skeptical and pragmatic-emotional.

Keywords: rational-critical voters, traditional-skeptical voters, pragmatic voters

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1. Introduction

Voter behavior is a picture of the political choices implemented by community groups in using their political rights. Where the use of political rights will give birth to political culture. Theoretically, according to political scientists, what is meant by political culture is the implementation of the values of political beliefs, feelings and attitudes carried out by voters on their emotional manifestations to political contestants, to realize voter orientation on their perceptions in order to achieve common goals politically in the form of joint policy making and regulation (Kantaprawira, 1983; Dahl, 1992; Almond, 1984; Macridis, 1996).

Almond (1984) states that in political culture always emphasizes some aspects of actual behavior in political action. On the other hand, political culture must also emphasize its non-actual aspects or sides such as regarding beliefs, political values, political attitudes and political orientation. In principle, political culture if examined from a psychological perspective is a political system that has a very important role. Therefore in the political system some of its main components are political structure and function. If so, we can conclude that the political system is a major component in understanding the political culture of a society. The political system is considered capable of giving us an understanding of how later the attitudes and political orientation of individuals are able to give birth to political culture.

Regarding the attitudes and political orientation of individuals and groups in political culture, the results of research by Almond and Verba (1983) classify this orientation into three main forms, namely: cognitive orientation is knowledge that is owned by the community regarding their belief in politics. Affective orientation is a picture of people's feelings for the political system, the role of the political system, political actors, political styles and political institutions such as political parties, the executive, legislative and judiciary. Evaluative orientation relates to opinions and decisions about political objects based on the standard of values and criteria for their feelings towards the holding of elections and information they know about politics (Maksudi, 2013).

Political culture is a picture of the political orientation and political attitudes of citizens towards political life in a country, region and region. The political orientation and political attitudes of the citizens of the community are closely related to the factors of trust and value to the political system that is implemented, in order to achieve political goals together by using a good political mechanism. To make the political system good, it must be supported by other systems that exist in the community such as social systems, cultural systems, good economic conditions, political education, political environment and geographical factors as well as other factors.

Political science always experiences development every time according to what factors are used to analyze these political events. Nowadays geographical factors are also used as one perspective in studying political science. The geographical approach to politics emphasizes several things related to the growth of population, location and

character of an area, environmental conditions and natural structures, the economic system in which the community resides. According to the perspective of political geography that the location of the settlement area will influence the political attitudes that will be taken by the community as a form of their political characteristics.

Political geography study is actually a development of political analysis that connects reciprocal relations between people's lives and political activities referring to the natural state of a region, country and region where political communities live. Referring to the opinion expressed by Ratzel (2007) this phenomenon is known as the organic state. As an object of study in political geography, the state was then understood as a unity of political society that has its own uniqueness, cultural homogeneity and individualistic character. To analyze a country, several aspects that must be the main factors include the shape of the territory of the country, the area, the location of a region; these are all space factors according to the terms delivered by Carlson (Hayati and Yani, 2007).

Political participation of citizens can be demonstrated by their involvement in the implementation of elections to elect people who have the competence to represent them in the legislature. General elections are also one way to make changes in leadership democratically. Democracy in general elections has always been identified with procedural models of democracy. It is procedural because the political participation of the people only comes to choosing the people they give the mandate to represent them, after that the authority is in the hands of the people they choose. This means that democracy can be regarded as one method in politics to conduct leadership circulation. Whereas then the follow-up of the will of the people in the process of administering the government is entirely in the hands of the people's representatives and leaders resulting from the electoral process. This indicates that the will of the people is a result of the political process (Schumpeter, 1942; Dahl, 1992; Linz, 1996).

General elections are a manifestation of procedural democracy; theoretically this democracy has at least four forms. First, the form of guardianship (delegation) is characterized by elections which prioritize deliberation in taking decisions as an embodiment of the trusteeship system. Second, the form of representation is characterized by the selection of direct leaders and the mechanism for making each decision using a representative system. Third, the form of consultation (deliberative) is a political mechanism or method in the selection of leaders using methods of deliberation and regulation in a participatory and direct manner. Finally, the form of direct democracy (participatory) is the mechanism of direct election of leaders, while to make regulations, decisions and policies are implemented in a participatory manner by involving many people (Suyatno, 2004).

Procedural democracy in principle is only as a medium or a way to put someone in a political and public office who is given the authority to make, implement, regulate and evaluate policies relating to the interests of the people. The community is only involved in the process, while at the implementation level after they are elected, the function of the community as the person who gives authority can not be used again.

Both those who hold positions as legislative and executive members are elected through political mechanisms that uses a system of procedural democracy.

Whereas to select those who have the right to participate in political contestation through the mechanism of elections whose election involves the community as the implementation of procedural democracy is the authority of political parties. Because this is related to the main tasks and functions of political parties, namely carrying out recruitment, education, socialization, communication and political cadre (Surbakti, 1992). This means that based on its function, political parties are expected to be able to produce cadres who have political sensitivity, to become leaders and representatives of the community who not only care but also understand what is the aspirations of the community to be implemented in the administration of government. Because basically the government is a combination of the executive and the legislature which has a regulatory function which means organizing the life of the state, empowerment that is able to increase the dignity of the people and their country and services, namely managing the management of good services to the community and serving well (Riwokaho and Haryanto, 1997).

Based on the explanation above, we can say that political parties have a very big role in the life of the state. Political parties must be well organized, have a clear political orientation, have values that can be guided by cadres, sympathizers and their followers. As well as political parties must also have visionary ideals which means broad reach and have a very far-sighted future in the interests of the nation and state. By definition political parties according to Neuman (1963) are an articulate organization, meaning an organization of active political actors who have a specific orientation to obtain, implement, maintain and perpetuate the power of government. And they compete to get the mandate from the community to run the government. In addition, we can also say that political parties as a liaison group between the interests of social ideology, the power of society and government institutions that are legally granted by the constitution widely (Budiardjo, 1998). That is why every political party must have an ideology or ideas or ideas and fundamental values related to the political party's actions or direction. Theoretically according to political parties based on their ideology consists of proto party, cadre, mass, dictatorial and catch all (Amal, 1996).

If we refer to the understanding of political parties, then automatically political parties need the name of political participation from the public. This participation is related to how much legitimacy political parties have in the eyes of the public. This legitimacy was not just born in the midst of the community but requires hard work from the administrators, cadres, sympathizers and followers of political parties. The basis is that good performance from political parties will give birth to a strong legitimacy for political parties and broad support from the public, especially related to policies that have been made by political parties. If the policies made by political parties benefit the interests of the people more then it will naturally have an electoral impact on the party concerned.

Political participation is an activity carried out by the community to be involved in the political process and administration. Whether it influences or gives input into policy making that will be implemented by the government through political mechanisms such as being involved in political discussions, hearings on the general policy-making process to influence the decision of the election of government leaders. At another level political participation can also be in the form of obedience of citizens to the implementation of policies that have been made by the government which are the responsibility of citizens. There are several forms of activities related to citizen political participation, including:

- 1) influencing the political process;
- 2) involved in policy making, implementing policies and other related activities by submitting claims openly;
- 3) actively paying taxes which are their responsibility;
- 4) implement a mutually agreed decision;
- 5) submit criticism to the government and political institutions;
- 6) actively involved in the process of correcting the implementation of general policies implemented by the government;
- 7) protest, pro and contra the prospective leaders submitted by political parties;
- 8) propose alternative leaders and politicians who will sit as representatives of the people during the ongoing political process and so on. (Surbakti, 1992)

Based on the level of awareness in participating, political participation according to McClosky (1972) is an action carried out by community members voluntarily to elect a ruler through a mechanism of general election either directly or indirectly. Whereas seen from the validity of political participation according to Nie and Verba (1975) relating to actions or activities carried out by citizens to be involved in the selection process of candidates for state officials through activities that citizens carry out according to applicable regulations. Meanwhile other political experts namely Huntington and Nelson (1994) said that what was meant by political participation was an activity affecting the formulation of policies by the government carried out on behalf of individuals by citizens. This means that all political experts agree that activities in such participation can be carried out personally or in groups, legally or not, spontaneously or in an organized manner and useful or not useful (Budiardjo, 1998). To see the form of political participation there are at least some basis that we can use to see it, among others, as follows based on their involvement, the dimensions of social stratification, their attitudes, their numbers (Surbakti, 1992).

Political participation in a democratic system is a necessity to be carried out regardless of the form of political participation. But in each activity political participation will give birth to its own characteristics depending on the context in which political participation is carried out. This context of participation will also help political observers and politicians to map the political behavior of the people in a region, region or country.

In this study the author wants to see how what factors influence voter behavior in watersheds in the 2014 legislative elections. The object of this research is the people who live in the Mentaya river basin, Kotawaringin Timur. Given that the Kotawaringin Timur district is very broad, this study specializes in electoral communities III in Baamang sub-district. Baamang sub-district is one of the sub-districts located in the Mentaya river basin, Kotawaringin Timur Regency. There are some interesting things to do research on the behavior of voters in the watershed according to the author, among others because of each legislative election in Kotawaringin Timur district where most of the people live in the Mentaya watershed there are no political parties that achieve more dominant results. The phenomenon of the absence of dominance of the dominant party is very interesting to study according to the author both for scientific and political purposes.

Kotawaringin Timur Regency is one of the developing districts in Central Kalimantan. Most economic developments enter through the Mentaya river. This means that we can say that the Mentaya River is the main economic access in Kotawaringin Timur and Kalimantan Tengah. Because in and out of goods sent using transfortasi water that comes from outside the island of Borneo the entrance through the sea port that is on the Mentaya river.

Geographically, most of the sub-districts in Kotawaringin Timur regency are in the Mentaya river basin, including Teluk Sampit sub-district, South Mentaya Hilir, Hanaut Island, North Hilata, Mentawa Baru Ketapang, Baamang, Seranau, Kota Besi, Mentaya Hulu, Telaga Antang and Antang Kalang sub-district. This means that 65% of the sub-districts in Kotawaringin Timur Regency are in the Mentaya River basin. Where in the study of political geography, the area of a region determines the behavior, dynamics and political choices of its people.

Like the characteristics of cities and settlements in other Kalimantan regions, the majority of the population lives or lives in the riverbanks. This is because the economic flow at that time can only be accessed through river channels, which connect one area to another. Although in its development later, the main connecting lines between the regions with each other in the Kotawaringin Timur regency can be passed by using land and air lines.

The legislative candidates offered by political parties participating in the general election in 2014 in Kotawaringin Timur Regency have diverse backgrounds. Both their educational and professional backgrounds, ranging from those with an equivalent high school education to a degree with an equivalent degree. Based on his profession, there are legislative candidates who become entrepreneurs, former officials, retired Indonesian national soldiers/Police of the Republic of Indonesia, up to farmers. This means that the community is given a lot of options by political parties to determine who is eligible to be their representative in parliament.

Baamang Subdistrict is one of the electoral districts in Kotawaringin Timur, namely Electoral District (III). Baamang Subdistrict is also one of the sub-districts in the Mentaya River, the largest and longest river in the Kotawaringin Timur regency. The

Baamang sub-district community is very diverse with a very multi-ethnic professional background, education, religion, culture and ethnicity. The plurality of community backgrounds is also one of the authors' choices to make Baamang sub-district the object of the author's research in order to see the behavior and political motives of voters in watersheds in the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur.

Based on this information, the community, especially those in the Mentaya river basin, have their own expectations of the legislative candidates who they deem fit to be their representatives. Although we realize that theoretically there are several problems that are always faced by society in determining social choices such as problems regarding the distribution of rights, the ability of leaders to control group actions, intellectual differences between individuals in society, decision making, ethics and so on (Coleman, 2011). These differences will then give birth to different characteristics between one community group and the other community groups.

2. Methods

This research uses descriptive qualitative approach. The location of this study is the community members who have the right to vote in the Electoral District III in Baamang Sub-District, Kotawaringin Timur Regency, Kalimantan Tengah Province, which lives in the Mentaya River basin. The choice of place of research is based on several factors such as a very diverse population both culturally, education, economic, social and so on. The second factor is that in general there are no political parties capable of winning a dominant vote in legislative elections. The third factor, aspects of affordability of research access.

The primary data source of the study was the result of interviews with several informants whose authors considered knowing the information the authors hoped for and the results of observations in the field by making observations directly from the behavior of voters involved in the 2014 legislative elections in Baamang sub-district, Kotawaringin Timur.

Secondary data from written documents or manuscripts made by the General Election Commission of Kotawaringin Timur Regency related to the implementation of the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur Regency. The researcher acts as a human instrument with supporting instruments in the form of interview guidelines, observation guidelines, and documentation guidelines. Analysis Qualitative research data is carried out through several main stages, namely carrying out organizing data, explaining it into research units, compiling research syntheses, making research patterns, selecting materials needed in research and finally concluding research results. The results of the 2014 Kotawaringin Timur Regency election can be seen on the website of Kotawaringin Timur Regency KPU. This research is limited to a discussion of the forms and factors that influence the behavior of voters in the watershed in the 2014 election of Kotawaringin Timur Regency.

3. Research Findings

3.1 Factors Affecting Voter Behavior

A. Similarity of Background Identity

Background identity is one of the factors that influence voter political choices. This identity bond is culturally more powerful than other factors that influence one's political choices. Identity similarity is characterized by recognition that identifies someone with other people based on lineage, ethnic background, similarity in culture, language, religion and even behavior.

In the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur district, especially in the Electoral District III in Baamang district, the use of identity politics was very thick. Especially the ethnic background, so the campaign material used by the candidates uses their respective ethnic cultural identities. The language that is often used to attract and attract voters is to use the term "uluh itah" which if translated into Bahasa Indonesia means "orang kita".

In addition, the background of tribal identity is also used by legislative candidates to shape their image and build their identity so that they can be closer to the voter community and eventually will get political support from the voters. There are many ways used by legislative candidates to build this tribal identity, among others, by attracting ethnic lineages they have as well as relatives and their families. For example, the lineage of the wife, husband, wife and husband and other kinship lines based on their ethnic and ethnic identity background.

This recipe is quite effective in gaining support from voters, especially those who are still traditional and see ethnic and ethnic backgrounds as a factor in determining their political choices. This line of kinship based on ethnic and tribal backgrounds by legislative candidates is continuously capitalized as capital to get closer to the voters and become an effective recipe for getting political support from voters who are in the Mentaya river basin in Baamang district, Kotawaringin Timur district. Starting from the capitalization of the ethnic background of the indigenous people of the Mentaya watershed such as Dayak to the ethnic tribes of immigrants who settled in Baamang sub-district such as Javanese, Madurese, Sundanese, Bugis, Batak and other tribes. The approach taken by legislative candidates starts from the personal (person to person) approach, institutionally (person to institution) through direct contact with regional organizations, institutions and associations.

On the other hand, people who ethnically have representatives in the Regional House of Representatives of Kotawaringin Timur Regency feel proud, because they feel there is hope that their fate will be constitutionally protected and noticed by the government at least in the issue of social security development and infrastructure development supporting income increases and their economy. Most of the immigrant ethnic settlers who live in the Baamang sub-district are engaged in the business sector, this security guarantee about business sustainability is then needed by them.

B. Educational Background of Candidates

Educational background of candidates in the 2014 general election in Kotawaringin Timur district, voter III area of Baamang sub-district varies greatly from equivalent high school education to master education (Strata 2/S2). Most of the candidates in electoral district III have a Bachelor's education background (S1). Based on interviews conducted by the author with several informants that their political choices are due to the educational background of the candidates. According to them, the educational background of a legislative candidate greatly determines the direction of policy and the ability to accommodate channel and process the aspirations channelled by the community.

Educational background will also be able to process aspirations into policies that are more pro-people. Especially to create community welfare, the availability of economic supporting infrastructure and the provision of supporting educational facilities. And more important is the ability of candidates to conduct supervision, rule-making and budgeting. This competence is only possessed by candidates who have an adequate background. This means that with an educational background that is adequate the ability to accommodate, channel and process aspirations into policies related to the public interest according to most voters is only owned by those who have an adequate educational background.

This factor is seen at least during the campaign carried out by legislative candidates, both institutionally, through political party institutions and personally when they interact and communicate with voters. Where those who have an educational background are only equal to Senior High School, most of their communication styles and patterns are different from those with an educational background Strata I and above. There is a kind of rigidity in communicating and speaking in public and most of them during the campaign is mostly just being passive and unable to express their ideas or ideas in a straightforward manner. Although not all are like that, most have this attitude, so there is doubt from voters to elect them. The hope of most Mentaya watershed communities is that in the future the political parties in choosing candidates for the legislature can be seen from their educational background, at least their last education is Strata I and above.

C. Background of the Candidate's Experience

Another factor that also determines people's political choices is the background of the candidates' experience. The experience intended is the experience of organization, community, socializing and interacting with candidates in the midst of society. This means that the communication style of candidates is very decisive and whether a candidate is elected and in general the community likes candidates who have good interacting experiences.

Another method used by citizens to see the experience of candidates is the ability of candidates to provide solutions to various kinds of problems that are asked by voters

when a dialogical campaign is conducted. The average legislative candidate who answers well the questions of the community is elected as a member of the legislature.

According to the majority of Mentaya watershed communities, the experience of candidates is at least able to forge candidates in making decisions, political attitudes and political alignments to the community. Because they already know and have good experience from the process of their interaction with the community. The experience of candidates if packaged and capitalized properly, can be a good political capital to get support in the form of votes in the conduct of general elections. From the information provided by the speakers in this study, not all candidates have experiences that are in line with the expectations of the community.

D. Economic Factors

Economic factors or the provision of money made by legislative candidates, better known as the attack of dawn is another motivation of determining the political choices of citizens in the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur regency. In particular for the electoral district III in Baamang sub-district the average range issued by candidates to carry out the dawn attack (Serangan Fajar) is 50,000 IDR to 250,000 IDR per voter.

“Serangan Fajar” or the distribution of money carried out by the legislative candidates is highly anticipated by the residents, and even in one area in the electoral district III of the Baamang sub-district blatantly said that they would not exercise their voting rights if there were no rewards from the candidates. On the other hand competition between candidates also determines the size of the money received by the community. The character of the community like this, in the sense that they will exercise their right to vote if there are cash rewards given by the legislative candidates who are very happy if the candidates who come to their environment are more than one candidate. They will conduct transactions to determine how much one vote is in their environment and they will choose candidates who provide a greater amount of money for them.

Based on the results of the research that the authors did that to ensure that the provision of money politics is effective and provides a large electoral impact for candidates. Candidates make a special team to carry out the dawn attack, meaning that each environment to be distributed with money each has its own coordinator. Each of these coordinators oversees 10-25 potential voters and they will be given money after they vote.

The pragmatic attitude of the community is also inseparable from the various backgrounds of legislative candidates, both from the aspects of education, experience, and human resources of less qualified candidates. So they take shortcuts to reach and get voter support, namely to distribute money in return for voting by voters. For the pragmatic community or voters, the behavior of candidates who are like this is very much awaited, because according to them that if they are elected there is a tendency for the elected candidates to forget them. Often when these legislative candidates have

been elected, come to listen to their aspirations through a mechanism that has only been guaranteed by law, namely recesses are rarely carried out.

E. Program, Vision and Mission of Candidates

The legislative program, vision and mission are still one of the assessments given by the community to determine their political choices. This type of society is seen from an educational background and personal experience, the average community that has adequate education and access to information is very large. To determine political choices, they first read, listen and even dialogue with candidates about the program, vision and mission if the candidates are elected. The ability of candidates to describe, explain and socialize the program, its vision and mission is one of the more points for the community to determine their political choices. But based on the results of this study, not all candidates are able to describe, explain and socialize the program, vision and mission well.

According to the speakers in this study the program offered by most candidates is a political party program that has not been able to be translated properly by candidates to be part of their program personally. This means that the political party program should be translated or reduced to be a personal program of candidates who in time if they are elected, they will implement the program for the benefit of many people. Whereas the candidates' vision and mission should be the development or modification of the vision and mission of political parties, but its nature is more implementable or easy to implement. In the 2014 legislative elections in Baamang sub-district not all candidates had the capabilities mentioned above. This factor also influenced people's choices in the 2014 general election in the Mentaya watershed in Baamang sub-district.

F. Disappointment with Legislative Member Performance Previously

One of the determinants of people's political choices is disappointment with the performance of previous legislative members, meaning that they are based on the analysis that the contributions made by previous legislators cannot be felt and seen. This disappointment also turned their support to other new candidates. According to them, the new candidates have more hope to fight for their aspirations.

Based on information provided by voters there is a tendency after elected legislators never again visit them and listen to their aspirations. Whereas if there are recess activities conducted by members of the legislature, they do not directly come to the community who once gave their support to them. Recess activities according to most communities are only mere ceremonial activities and where the activities are held in the sub-district office. Usually those invited to attend the recess activities are only certain groups, such as the village head, to the village and government structural officials.

G. Based on the Popularity and Appearance of Candidates

The results of this study found that one of the determinants of people's political choices was the popularity and appearance of candidates. This means that what they choose is a public figure, candidates who have a handsome and beautiful appearance even though they do not know the candidate. This choice is according to them because of the lack of information they receive about candidates who participate in political contestation. In addition, what is important according to them is that political choices are determined by whether or not a candidate is viewed physically.

In a society like this, candidates who have handsome and beautiful faces have the opportunity to get voters' votes. Whereas the legislative candidates who do not have adequate and good looks are deemed not chosen by them. Voters who use this factor are mostly beginner voters and teenagers, housewives and members of communities who uphold appearance such as the community of salon business associates, young people who love motor sports and extremes and so on.

4. Discussion

4.1 Political Choice Motives Political Motives for Choosing the Edge of the Mentaya River Society

The Mentaya river basin community is an open society, as is the type of coastal community. They are easy to adapt to any group of people, culture, ethnicity and religion, provided that while living in a community they do not interfere with each other. This tendency was carried on the determination of their political attitudes and choices in the implementation of the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur regency, Election III district, Baamang sub-district.

At least this was marked by the absence of a dominant party in obtaining seats in the Rakyat Representative Council in the Kotawaringin Timur regency. In the III electoral district of Baamang sub-district, seven political parties each placed one representative in the regional parliament. The inability of the party to dominate votes is due to the open character of the riverbanks, there are materialistic, rational, idealistic and apathetic tendencies.

If there are political parties that are able to win votes and place their representatives in the legislature in the 2014 general election, they are mostly determined by money politics. Because most of the voters' backgrounds use their voting rights because of the lure to get substitute money for work on election day. The amount received by voters in this category is between 100,000 and 250,000 per person. Economically, we can imagine how much the political costs incurred by the legislative candidates to get a vote in the Mentaya river.

According to voters in this category, the rewards they get from giving candidates are very rational and reasonable, because on the same day they do not work. Even though they need costs to meet their daily needs, such as to buy cigarettes, rice, children's milk and so on. If they do not work, they will not get money instead of being

fair if the candidates give money in return for them according to the interviewees interviewed by the author.

In other community groups ditepian Mentaya river there are still people who make their choices based on the program, vision and mission of the candidates. If according to the program, the candidates' vision and mission do not provide positive effectiveness for the development of their region, then they will not support the candidates. The candidates who socialize the program, their vision and mission to the community included in this category, in the end to get voter support, will make a political contract, namely the implementation of the program agreement, vision and mission if elected as legislative members. If the elected candidates do not implement the political contract that they have agreed to, then in the next election the legislative members will not be supported again.

Based on the results of this study in the previous sub-chapter and by referring to the results of the 2014 legislative elections for the Mentaya watershed community in Baamang sub-district there are at least seven motives that influence their political choices, among others, first, the similarity of background identity. Political identity cannot be separated from the political culture of watershed communities. In the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur regency, Kalimantan Tengah province, voter III in the sub-district of Baamang was still very much carried out by legislative candidates in order to get voter support. Their background of ethnicity and ethnic identity is capitalization into political capital to identify themselves with voters. They feel part of a particular ethnicity or ethnicity with the lineage that they take both personally and kinship lines that come from their wives, husbands, siblings, wives and husbands, grandparents, as well as other ethnicity lineage bases.

This effort in the 2014 legislative elections in Kotawaringin Timur district was quite successful and became a model in every general election. As a result, before the election began political bases based on ethnicity sprung up like mushrooms in the rain. Starting from the local ethnic group of Dayak people with the smallest sub-groups of Dayak and other ethnic groups such as Javanese, Minang, Sundanese, Batak, Madurese, Bugis, Balinese and not to miss various kinds of regional-based fraternal associations. Such as the Dayak Customary Council, the Central Kalimantan Dayak Regional Consultative Council, the Madurese Family Association, and various regional organizations, associations and associations. Where the end of all this is boiled down to tribal identity and ethnicity which was deliberately created in order to gain support for political contestations called legislative elections and other political contestations.

Second, the educational background of candidates. Education of candidates is the criteria used by voters to determine their political choices. In the majority of voters in the Mentaya watershed in Baamang sub-district, background issues in education are one of the main indicators in determining their political choices. Because they assume the higher the education of a legislative candidate, the greater their hopes of obtaining guarantees of articulating their interests through the process of policy formulation that will be carried out by candidates if they are elected later. Vice versa, the lower the

education of the legislative candidates, the lower the ability of candidates to be able to contribute maximally in the formulation of policies relating to the interests of many people. For this reason, according to them, they will see legislative candidates, one of them is from an educational background owned by candidates. Although not all candidates who have a high or minimum education, Strata I and above have all the abilities they expect. But at least the candidates who have higher education have experience and knowledge based on their knowledge how to do good policy formulation, implement a clean country and understand the needs needed by the community.

Third, the background of the experience of candidates. The experience of legislative candidates desired by voters in the Mentaya river basin is the experience of candidates interacting and communicating with the community. This process can be known by the community from an organizational background that is owned by candidates, the more active candidates in community organizations, the greater the chance of candidates to be elected. This experience later according to the voters will be able to deliver selected candidates to make various kinds of policy formulations relating to the interests of society at large. Because candidates who have organizational experience and interact with the community already have capital in the form of aspirations he hears directly from the public when they communicate in community organizations forums. There are very many types of community organization forums starting from organizations with ethnicity, ethnicity, regionalism, religion, profession, hobbies, sports, education and so on. Where all types of organizations provide good experience to legislative candidates as capital if elected as legislators later. Like the character of the coastal community in general which is open, the people of the Mentaya river basin also have the same level. This attitude then gave birth to various organizations that grew and developed in the midst of society. As well as making the organization as one of the political capital that is capitalized sustainably for the political interests of candidates and political parties in political contestation.

Fourth, encouraging economic factors. Economic factors are another term to describe the events of money politics that developed amid the Mentaya river basin communities. We cannot deny that money politics is still growing rapidly and is challenging the legislative political contest in 2014 in Kotawaringin Timur, especially in the electoral district III in Baamang sub-district. Money politics is the ultimate weapon that is most effective to be used by legislative candidates in order to get voter support. The amount of the money politics range is between 100,000-250.000 IDR/person given by candidates. Even though not all candidates do money politics and not all voters accept the award of candidates. But most of the people who are pragmatic and seen from their social status are those who are under the poverty line, with professions as farmers, fishermen, laborers, traders, construction workers, artisans, and so forth. Where according to them the value of 100,000-250,000 IDR is a pretty big number in exchange for not working on polling day.

Fifth, the candidates' programs, vision and mission. The legislative candidates program, vision and mission are one of the motives that make the Mentaya watershed community give their support and political choices to candidates. This is because voters assume that candidates have the ability to communicate and explain the program, vision and mission of course candidates who have quality. This personal quality is inseparable from the attitudes and behaviors that are good for the candidates. This personal quality, attitude and good behavior is the basic capital that can be held and used by voters to overcome the candidates who have and belong to this category deserve to be elected. Quantitatively, the number of candidates who have qualifications like this is very small, even according to some informants in this study because too little can be calculated using the fingers. This statement according to the author is a form of pessimistic attitudes towards the quality of candidates offered by political parties to voters. As a result, most of the legislative candidates personally did not have adequate qualifications and even impressed political parties only to fulfill the administrative quota for regulation on the process of illegal logging so that political parties were allowed to participate in political contestations. This opinion is due to the lack of candidates who have the ability to communicate and communicate their programs, vision and mission well with straightforward language, easily digestible by voters if they are elected to the legislature.

Sixth, disappointment with the performance of the previous period legislators. Another motive that determines the political attitudes and political choices of the Mentaya watershed community is disappointment with the performance of previous legislative members. Changes in political support and political choice in the 2014 legislative elections cannot be separated from the performance of the previous period legislators. This assessment was carried out by the Mentaya watershed community to elected and elected legislators who rarely communicated and even seemed to have never met their boarders. This includes the recess which is constitutionally mandated by law concerning the main duties and responsibilities of legislative members. Whereas if they carry out the invited recess, only government officials and their implementation are in government offices. Not immediately came the bags of voices or constituents who had previously supported and voted for them. This attitude later became one of the reasons why voter political support changed in the 2014 general election.

Finally, based on the popularity and appearance of candidates. The last motive affecting the voting behavior of the Mentaya river basin community in the 2014 legislative elections was the popularity and appearance of candidates. The popularity of candidates can be seen from how far a candidate is known in the community. While the appearance of candidates is related to the physical form of a legislative candidate, if he is a male then they must be dashing and have a dashing, handsome and befitting face, on the contrary if the candidate is a woman, the demand must be beautiful. The good looks and beauty of the legislative candidates is also one of the determining factors in making political choices in the 2014 legislative elections for people living in the Mentaya river basin. The political choice is based on the appearance or appearance of

these candidates, due to the lack of knowledge of the voters regarding the political background of candidates and political education that is not optimally run by political parties.

4.2 Types of Community Voters Edge of the Mentaya River Stream

Based on the involvement of voters in political activities, political participation given by voters can be categorized as passive-shaped voters. This means that the involvement in the legislative general election process specifically to elect their representatives in the Kotim Regency DPRD in 2014 is not on its own consciousness, but because there is encouragement from other parties. According to the informants interviewed by the author there were several reasons why they were involved in the electoral process, among others, as follows first, because there were their families who ran for membership in the Regency DPRD. Kotim. Second, there are also voters who say the reason they are involved is because there are rewards promised by the legislative candidates. Third, there are also voters who choose because they are invited by others and their choice follows the choices of those who invite them. Fourth, the reason for choosing election is because it is encouraged by other parties, especially people who have influence in the community such as religious leaders, community leaders, traditional leaders, leaders of organizations and rich local people and so on.

Based on the dimensions of social stratification, voters participating in the 2014 legislative election process in Kotawaringin Timur regency can be grouped into citizens, marginal groups (groups that have very little contact with the political system) and isolated groups (groups that rarely participate). This means that in the process or political activity, they do not have the power to influence the process or political activity itself. This is at least the first, revealed by the opinions expressed by voters, that most of their citizens are not administrators of political parties, community organizations and have connections to the government. Second, the majority of voters are workers in the private sector and never involve themselves in the activities of community organizations, political parties and so on. But they have their own analysis of seeing the activities and political processes that are running. They are also one of the potential groups to be influenced by legislative candidates. Like what one of the transport workers found in the market in the Baamang sub-district. They are often visited by legislative candidates both during the campaign and during quiet times. Almost all legislative candidates who come to their place of work almost all distribute t-shirts, calendars, umbrellas and other souvenirs in which there are pictures/photos, serial numbers and party bearers of the legislative candidates.

Based on the explanation above, the type of Mentaya river flow selector in Kotawaringin Timur Regency is influenced by several factors, namely based on their involvement, social stratification, attitude, and number. Based on the results of interviews conducted by the authors, most voters said that their participation was passive because of the encouragement from other parties, not on the basis of their own awareness. Such as the existence of kinship relations with legislative candidates, the

influence of religious, customary, organizational leaders and invited by friends. In addition to the invitation from other parties, other factors that determine people's political choices as a representation of their political participation because of political transactions such as money politics are neatly packaged and difficult to prove legally. Based on the acknowledgment of some informants it is difficult to prove that the name money politics is because between the candidates and recipients maintain the confidentiality of the transaction. Although this study does not measure the quality of voter political participation, but with information such as the authors finding in the field, most voters' political participation falls into the low category.

The negative impact of passive voter political participation is the low level of public control over Parliament's performance and the absence of a permanent, sustainable and performance-based political contract between candidates and voters. Another thing that might happen after the candidates get their power, they cannot carry out their functions properly. Because it was started with the intention to return funds issued during the nomination and campaign period. In the study of political psychology this phenomenon is part of the deviation of the behavior of state and government officials. The final result is the performance of DPRD members who are expected to be maximal to voice the aspirations of the community, especially their constituents, if they are held hostage by the desire to return the capital invested during the political process.

Based on the observations of the authors in the field there are several factors that make voter political participation passive which can be divided into two, namely from the inside (internal) environment of the community and from the outside (external). Internally there are at least two factors that influence, among others, firstly, the factors of education, knowledge and experience of the people themselves. Second, the social environment and voter residence. According to contemporary political studies, the education factor, both obtained through formal and informal education and the environment in which people or groups of people interact, have a direct influence on the quality and form of voter political participation. Because the educational background will be able to filter information provided by politicians during political activities. Whereas externally the factors that influence are the weak machinery of political parties carrying out one of the functions, namely implementing education to voters. In addition, it is also due to the lack of social organizations in providing political enlightenment to voters.

Based on the discussion above and with the plurality of people living in the Mentaya river area using theoretical analysis knives can be categorized into several types of voters namely first, rational and critic Voter, this is indicated by the presence of voters who consider the program, the candidates' vision and mission. This rational consideration is to build a political contract between the constituents and the legislative candidates so that the candidates' programs, vision and mission will have to be implemented.

Second, traditional-skeptical voters, namely voters who determine their political choices because of the closeness of traditional and cultural, so that they use this capital to determine their political choices without considering the candidates' programs, vision and mission. Historically the closeness that they built has indeed been long and the content of this closeness later became their political capital to campaign for the legislative candidates they were carrying out. But when asked about the program, the candidates' vision and mission were unable to explain clearly. In general, the voters who are in this category are very skeptical about the discourse raised by other candidates who are the opponents and the rivalries of their legislative candidates and they do not ignore the other legislative candidates' figures.

Third, pre-emotional voters, namely voters who only make their choices because there are frills and reciprocity in the form of material provided by candidates. This pragmatic attitude is psychologically driven by the emotional encouragement of voters who only consider the material interests of the candidates for a moment. This transactional politics is increasingly becoming a political trend among the riverside community of Mentaya because candidates who build their political careers instantly.

5. Conclusion

There are at least three forms of voting behavior in the community in the Mentaya river basin. First, rational-critical voters, namely voters who still use their common sense to consider someone to be their representative in the Regional Representative Council. They still see, considering even discussing the vision made by the legislative candidates, the mission to be carried out by the legislative candidates after they are elected, the program that will be offered by the legislative candidates, they are still trying to explore the background of candidates, and other considerations that they think are rational to criticize before they dropping his choice on certain candidates.

Second, the traditionally skeptical character of the electorate is the type of voter who makes someone his political choice in legislative elections because of the close personal relationship, namely friendship and kinship, the similarity of cultural backgrounds with candidates and so on without considering whether the candidates they choose to be able to carry out their main tasks and functions as representatives of the people later.

Third, the character of the *praktis*-emotional voters, namely the type of voters who determine their political choices because there are material benefits that they get when the election takes place. The benefits obtained by the voters who enter this type are in the form of daily basic needs, tired money or substitute for work on that day or in the form of other materials provided by candidates. Emotional feelings to get this momentary advantage in general that encourage their emotions to determine their political choices.

In general, the characteristics of Mentaya watershed voters in Kotawaringin Timur regency are voters who are liquid, open and divided into three forms namely

rational-critical, traditional-skeptical and pragmatic-emotional. If the candidates want to enter and approach each of these voter groups, they must first understand their character's background.

5.1 Recommendations

This research is one of the studies that only wants to see the character of voters based on geography, not yet to measure how much the quality of voter participation. So in the next election it is expected that there are strategies that must be carried out by the legislative candidates regarding the findings of this study. First, to avoid high cost politics political parties must make several breakthroughs in carrying out the function of political education to the voting community. This education is carried out on an ongoing basis and must be a place for the implementation of political education as a place to instill ideological values of the party, so that voters can indirectly become cadres of the political party at least become sympathizers. This pattern according to the author is very suitable with the character of traditional voters who are skeptical and pragmatic. In terms of the number of voters who fall into this category very much and political parties may not feel tired to carry out their political education functions.

Secondly, political parties internally have to carry out cadres continuously by improving the quality of their cadres. At least the cadres of political parties must understand the basic ideology of their parties, the vision and mission that will be carried out by their parties, the party platform and the direction of the struggle of political parties must be understood by the cadres of political parties. In order for the characteristics of rational-critical voters political parties are able to gain votes from this category. Although there are not many in number, their opinions are very influential among watershed communities. Because the voters included in this category are leaders who are role models or places of society to discuss politics.

Third, while voters, especially voters who fall into the pragmatic-emotional category, must change their perspective on politics, not narrowly and short-term, but must be broad and far-sighted in the future. This means that money or material in any form is no longer their political orientation, because in the end this will also harm them in the long run. The task of providing political awareness is not just the task of political parties, but all stakeholders related to the administration of government and all components involved in the political system. With the aim that in the future there will be an increase in the quality of our political life, the implementation of democracy and the improvement of the quality of holding elections.

References

Almond, Gabriel A. 1984. *Budaya Politik: Tingkah Laku Politik dan Demokrasi di Lima Negara*. Bina Aksara: Jakarta.

- Almond, Gabriel A., and Sidney Verba. 1983. *The Civic Culture: Political Attitudes and Democracy in Five Nations*. Sage: Newbury Park.
- Amal, Ichlasul. 1996. *Teori-Teori Mutakhir Partai Politik*. PT Tiara Wacana Yogya: Yogyakarta.
- Budiardjo, Miriam. 1998. *Partisipasi dan Partai Politik*. Yayasan Obor Indonesia: Jakarta.
- Coleman, James S. 2011. *Dasar-Dasar Teori Sosial Foundations of Social Theory*. Nusa Media: Bandung.
- Dahl, Robert. 1992. *Demokrasi dan Para Pengkritiknya*. Yayasan Obor Indonesia: Jakarta.
- Hayati, Sri and Ahmad Yani. 2007. *Geografi Politik*. PT. Refika Aditama: Bandung.
- Kantaprawira, Rusadi. 1983. *Sistem Politik Indonesia Suatu Model Pengantar*. Sinar Baru: Bandung.
- Linz, Juan J. and Alfred Stepan. 1996. Toward Consolidated Democracies. *Journal of Democracy*, 7(2): 14-33.
- Macridis, C. Roy, and Brown, Bernard E. 1996. *Perbandingan Politik*. Erlangga: Jakarta.
- Maksudi, Beddy Iriawan. 2013. *Sistem Politik Indonesia Pemahaman Secara Teoritik dan Empirik*. PT. Rajawali Pers: Jakarta.
- McClosky, Herbert. 1972. *Political Participation*. *International Encyclopedia of the Social Science*. The Macmillan Company: New York.
- Nelson, Samuel P. Huntington and Joan. 1990. *Partisipasi Politik di Negara Berkembang*. Rineka Cipta: Jakarta.
- Neumann, S. 1963. Toward a Comparative Study of Political Parties. In: Eckstein, H. & Apter, D. E. (eds.) *Comparative Politics: A Reader*. The Free Press: New York.
- Nie, Norman H. and Sidney Verba. 1975. "Political Participation" in *Handbook of Political Science*, Fred I. Greenstone & Nelson W. Polsky (eds.), Addison-Wesley Publishing Company: Reading Mass.
- Riwokaho, Josef and Haryanto. 1997. *Fungsi-Fungsi Pemerintahan*. Badan Pendidikan dan Pelatihan Departemen Dalam Negeri: Jakarta.
- Schumpeter, J. 1942. *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Surbakti, Ramlan. 1992. *Memahami Ilmu Politik*. PT Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia: Jakarta.
- Suyatno. 2008. *Menjelajahi Demokrasi*. Humaniora: Bandung.

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